

Paper reviewing the landscape of knowledge networks for adaptation in Europe

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Author(s): Marta Bruno Soares,
Pierre Van Wolleghem Gavin
Lamb, Ivan Puga-Gonzalez, Eulàlia
Baulenas, Jonathan Ulrich, Sam Pickard,
Astrid Kause, LeRon Shults.

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Abbreviations Used

CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
EU	European Union
KH	Knowledge Hub(s)
KN	Knowledge Network(s)

1 Summary for Publication

This study captures the landscape of Knowledge Networks (KNs) supporting Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) in Europe. KNs can facilitate collaboration and knowledge-sharing amongst its members, which is critical for addressing the complex, multilevel challenges posed by climate change. The study employs systematic grey literature methods and identifies a total of 46 platforms, 32 of which are qualified as KNs and forms the core of the analysis presented, and 14 are information-focused Knowledge Hubs (KHs). The deliverable analyzes their geographic distribution, composition and activities.

KNs are primarily composed of local authorities (85%), with some including for-profit, non-profit, or research entities. Most are headquartered in Belgium, Germany, and France, but membership in this type of KNs is higher in Italy and Spain. Criteria and threshold to become a KN member vary, ranging from low-access networks like the Covenant of Mayors to higher-access ones like C40, which requires members to demonstrate climate leadership.

Key activities include the exchange of good practices, policy advocacy, and financial capacity-building. KNs help members secure funding, form consortia, and, in some cases, directly fund projects. Peer learning is a common feature, supported through conferences, thematic groups, and digital platforms. Some KNs provide symbolic capital, enhancing members' reputations via awards and visibility initiatives.

The study highlights the critical role of KNs in enabling climate adaptation but suggests room for improvement. Enhanced monitoring, greater inclusivity, and targeted support could help KNs address the unique, localized needs of their members, strengthening their overall impact on adaptation governance. Limitations of our study include reliance on English-language sources and limited feedback from KN members. Despite this, the findings provide valuable insights into the evolving landscape of climate-focused networks in Europe and how these play a critical role in supporting their members (particularly local authorities) in their adaptation journey.

2 Contribution to the top-level objectives of Impetus4Change

The Deliverable provides a comprehensive analysis of the landscape of KN operating in the field of CCA in Europe, thus directly supporting the objectives outlined in WP1 and T1.1. The lines that follow explain in detail how D1.1 meets the objectives of WP1 and T1.1 (see table below for a summary).

Mapping the Landscape of KNs: The document identifies 32 Knowledge Networks and 14 Knowledge Hubs, categorizing them based on their activities (e.g., advocacy, peer learning) and modes of operation (e.g., unidirectional knowledge dissemination or

multidirectional collaboration). This aligns with the task's aim to take stock of the current KN landscape.

Actor Analysis: It details the types of members in KNs, such as local authorities, non-profit organizations, for-profits, and research institutions. This includes an in-depth examination of member composition and representation across countries, addressing the task's focus on the actors involved.

Roles in Supporting Adaptation: The document explores how KNs support climate adaptation through activities like policy advocacy, financial capacity building, and knowledge circulation. This directly addresses the task's need to understand the role of KNs in supporting adaptation measures.

Governance Structures: KN governance models are described, including membership thresholds, and funding mechanisms. This insight supports the task's goal of analyzing how KNs are governed.

Use of Climate Information and Identified Needs: The document discusses the ways KNs facilitate knowledge sharing, use climate information, and support local authorities in addressing specific adaptation challenges. It also identifies gaps, such as limited monitoring of adaptation outcomes, contributing to understanding KNs' current needs.

The deliverable also provides insights to inform subsequent tasks, such as identifying relevant networks for engagement in T1.3 and T1.4.

2.1.1.1 Objective	2.1.1.2 Contribution from Deliverable
<p><u>Overall Objective:</u> WP1 aims to map, explore and understand how the flow, uptake and use of climate information and knowledge takes place within and across KN (and its actors) that are tasked to manage, implement and support climate change adaptation and build resilience in an unparalleled effort towards societal transformation across Europe.</p>	<p>D1.1 maps, categorizes and explores the landscape of KNs operating in the field of climate change adaptation in Europe.</p>
<p>T1.1 takes stock of the current landscape of KN operating in the climate change adaptation field across Europe. This information will allow us to review existing academic and grey literature to help understand this complex landscape including typologies of KN e.g., activist groups, youth organizations and networks,</p>	<p>D1.1 reviews academic and grey literature to take stock of the current KN landscape. Academic literature informs the analytical framework while grey literature allows the identification of KNs. The document identifies 32 KNs and 14 KHs categorizing them based on their activities (e.g. advocacy, peer learning) and modes of operation (e.g.</p>

communities of practice, social movements, journalists.	unidirectional knowledge dissemination or multidirectional collaboration).
Such a detailed review will include (i) the actors involved, (ii) their role in supporting climate change adaptation, (iii) how they are governed, and finally (iv) how they currently employ and use climate information and their needs to better support climate change adaptation measures.	D1.1 includes: i) the actors involved and provides a detailed and documented account of KN membership; ii) the role of KNs in supporting CCA through activities like policy advocacy, financial capacity building, and knowledge circulation; iii) KNs' governance structure including membership rules and funding mechanisms; and iv) the ways KNs facilitate knowledge sharing, and support local authorities in addressing adaptation challenges. It also suggests the existence of gaps, such as limited monitoring of adaptation outcomes, contributing to understanding KNs' current needs.
The findings from this task will help inform T1.3. and T1.4. in terms of identifying other potentially relevant KN that may be pertinent to engage with during those tasks.	D1.1's findings and data created inform the work being conducted in T1.2, T1.3 and T1.4.

3 The landscape of Knowledge Networks supporting climate adaptation in Europe

3.1 Introduction

The complex nature of climate change with its global reach and local impacts and the need for concerted action across actors and scales of governance makes this a super-wicked problem (Rittel and Webber, 1973; Levin et al., 2012). Such 'wickedness' demands alternative governance arrangements and practices involving actors across the public and private sectors to adequately address climate adaptation (Mees, 2017; IPCC, 2022). In Europe, climate adaptation is governed by a multi-scalar system of policies as well as governing modes, tools, and actors (cf. Bulkeley and Betsill, 2013; Storbjörk, 2007). These are influenced by a vertical dimension from the international sphere e.g. with the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (Galarraga et al., 2011), to the EU Adaptation Strategy at European level, down to the national and local levels although policy commitments and levels of intervention can vary greatly across Europe (Aguiar et al., 2018). Concomitantly, adaptation is also governed within horizontal dimensions such as through networks connecting actors in specific places or with a common goal (Giest and Howlett, 2013; Dawes et al., 2012).

Adaptation efforts also span a range of foci and goals e.g. policy, access to resources, risk reduction, advocacy, activism (Owen, 2020) but is ultimately context specific given differential vulnerabilities across communities, economic sectors, infrastructure, marginalised groups, etc (Petzold et al., 2023). At the sub-national level, the role of local authorities (LAs) is critical given their responsibilities in delivering critical public services (e.g. public health, social care, emergency services) which are often affected by climate impacts. Furthermore, they are also (often) incumbent to plan and implement adaptation measures and policy at local level (Mees, 2017; Petzold et al., 2023; Panenko et al., 2021; Celliers et al., 2021). However, LAs are also often constrained for resources and capacity to perform the assessments required whilst often overwhelmed by a plethora of concomitant issues. These include for example, the speed and magnitude of the changes required to address adaptation efforts (e.g. institutional, logistical, operational); the range of climate data and information, platforms, tools, and analytical approaches that can be used in the development of adaptation policy and strategies; competing pressures against limited financial resources (cf. Aguiar et al., 2018).

Access to useful and usable knowledge and information is critical to identify and prioritise policy interventions, strategies and adaptation measures (Dilling and Lemos, 2011). Moreover, connecting, sharing and learning with others can also be critical towards effective adaptation (Muccione et al, 2019; Dilling and Lemos, 2011; Bidwell et al., 2013). In this context, the role of networks in enabling knowledge creation and sharing, learning and governing climate adaptation can be key (Corfee-Morlot et al., 2011) and have been on the rise in Europe since the 1980s (Panenko et al., 2021; Fünfgeld, 2014; Giest and Howlett, 2013).

The study of networks has been pursued across a range of disciplines e.g. computer science, sociology, mathematics, political sciences, anthropology leading to a complex landscape of terminologies, conceptualisations and methodologies (Oliveira and Gama, 2012). In its most simplistic notion, a network is a group of points (also known as nodes, actors or agents) linked by lines (also known as edges, links or ties) and can be used to represent natural, technological and social systems (Newman, 2018; Henry and Vollan, 2014; Oliveira and Gama, 2012). A network can capture different properties and patterns of interaction within the system it seeks to represent.

In knowledge networks, the collaboration, exchange and circulation of information and knowledge amongst its members is a core characteristic (Creech et al., 2004). Due to their nature, these types of networks can also enable the creation of new understandings of a problem, identify solutions, support peer-to-peer learning and boost collective action all of which can be critical towards adaptation-related activities (cf. Henry and Vollan, 2014). Some see knowledge networks “(...) as vehicles for bridging the gap between knowledge and action.” (Feldman and Ingram, 2009, p.10). They can also be important mechanisms for governing climate change “(...) through the development of shared framings of policy problems and by creating collective senses of identity.” (Bulkeley et al., 2003, p. 241). This type of networks can therefore support and enable climate change adaptation policy and action (Muccione et al., 2019; Hauge et al., 2019) particularly in cases where network members have agency to act on the knowledge acquired such as in the case of transnational municipal networks (TMNs) (Fünfgeld, 2015, Bulkeley et al., 2003).

Albeit disciplinary differences, knowledge networks are composed of inherent characteristics such as their scope and aim (Hauge et al., 2018; Fünfgeld, 2015; Robins et al., 2011); membership conditions (Bulkeley et al., 2003; Creech et al., 2004; Fünfgeld, 2015); mechanisms for collaboration and knowledge sharing (Bulkeley et al., 2003; Muñoz-Erickson and Cutts, 2016; Robins et al., 2011; Henry and Vollan, 2014; Woodruff, 2020); and access to resources and support (Henry and Vollan, 2014; Creech et al., 2004; Fünfgeld, 2015; Kern and Bulkeley, 2009).

Despite the key role that knowledge networks have in helping govern and support climate adaptation, there is currently limited knowledge of the comprehensive landscape of this type of networks in Europe particularly over the last 10 years. This paper provides an up-to-date overview of this landscape and how current knowledge networks support their members on climate change adaptation. Section 3.2 describes the methodology pursued in this study; section 3.4.3 present key findings including general characteristics of the networks and the type of members before delving into those specifically supporting local authorities in their climate adaptation journey. Sections 3.4 and 3.5 provide a discussion and some conclusions, respectively.

3.2 Methodology

3.2.1. Network search

To identify existing knowledge networks operating within the field of climate change adaptation in Europe, we started by conducting an initial scoping review of relevant literature to help us identify potential networks of interest. To do so, we used Google Scholar and targeted keywords such as 'network', 'climate', 'knowledge', 'adaptation' and 'Europe'. From this initial review, a few KNs were identified including ICLEI, Climate Alliance, Fridays for Future, Reclaim the Power, Energy Cities, Union of the Baltic Cities, and Alliance in the Alps. However, given the non-academic nature of this type of knowledge networks and recognising that, nowadays, most of this type of networks have an online presence, we decided to pursue a more in-depth analysis of grey literature.

To search the grey literature, we used Google's advanced search function focusing on the English-language. As Google's search results are dependent on previous search history, browser version and geographic location (Mahood et al., 2012), our searches were run from anonymous browsers after caches and cookies were deleted, using Firefox and Chrome, from the UK and Norway. Considering the complexity of the subject matter and the potential for using different terms with similar meanings (e.g. adaptation and resilience) nine distinct keyword combinations relevant to climate knowledge networks were used to ensure a wider breath of coverage in terms of terminology (Table 1). A total of 2,084 results were identified after an initial screening of the nine variations of keywords.

Table 1 – Keyword search terms

Keywords used
knowledge AND network AND climate AND adapt* AND mitigate* AND Europe AND communication
climate AND adapt* AND group
climate AND adapt* AND association
climate AND adapt* AND community

climate AND adapt* AND movement
clima*AND risk AND network OR group OR association OR community OR movement
clima*AND resilien* AND network OR group OR association OR community OR movement
Europ* AND Resilien* AND Cities OR network
Europ* AND Sustainab* AND Cities OR network

Initial results were then subjected to multiple rounds of manual screening performed by three people in relation to a pre-defined set of inclusion criteria (see Table 2). This allowed us to identify relevant networks, including those based in Europe (or global networks but with a filial in Europe), operating in climate change adaptation-related areas, of practical nature¹, and providing an online presence. We also excluded online platforms operating at sub-national level to avoid biases towards local networks in the UK (due to the search being conducted in English) and to focus the analysis on networks operating at national and/or regional level.

Table 2 – Inclusion criteria applied to Google results

	Inclusion criteria
Region	Europe (including global initiatives with a European focus)
Topic	Cover climate change adaptation
Type of network	Focus on KN that operate on the ground i.e. of an empirical nature rather than with a theoretical development focus
Online presence	Provides an online space for 'storing, creating and sharing knowledge on climate change adaptation'
Scale of operations	Only networks operating at the national level or above

The application of the inclusion criteria helped reduce the results to 168 potential networks. We then conducted a final assessment to remove duplicates and conduct a more thorough case-by-case analysis (e.g. through analysis of websites or related documentation available online) and ended with 46 potential networks that matched our criteria (Appendix 1).

3.2.2. Network analysis

Once relevant networks were identified, we proceeded with collecting and analysing relevant data from the networks' websites based on an analytical framework developed by a team of experts in different disciplines (e.g. social sciences, political science, linguistics, and natural sciences). This analytical framework encompassed general characteristics (e.g. year of creation, scale of operations, aim and scope of the network) and other key themes often associated with this type of networks such as the structure of the network, membership, governance, internal communication and interaction between members, support to members (Creech and Ramji, 2004; Phelps et al., 2012).

The data collected was organized, categorized and stored in a standardized database geared towards comparison across KN. The database and codebook are freely accessible for research purposes at {link omitted for anonymity}

Using web scraping techniques, we also collected data on the member organisations of the knowledge networks identified. Using R and the Rvest package, we automated the extraction of platform members (along with basic information such as country and city in which they are located) from their website. The information collected was then supplemented with geo-coordinates (automated via R package tidygeocoder). The database counts a total of about 17,000 knowledge network members and is also freely available online.

The 46 knowledge networks identified in the literature review were initially classified according to their mode of collaboration (cf. Creech and Ramji, 2004) to help distinguish those focusing on knowledge dissemination in a unidirectional manner which we characterise as knowledge hubs (KH; n=14) and those focusing on pluri-directional collaboration between its members which we describe as knowledge networks (KN) in this study (n=32). Appendix 2 provides a detailed list of all the 46 KN and KH identified, and their categorisation based on their mode of collaboration. The remainder of this paper focuses on the 32 KN given their active and ongoing support to their members in relation to climate change adaptation efforts (Table 3).

Table 3 – Knowledge networks, types of members and geographical coverage

KN name	Main type of members (%)	Number of countries covered*
Alliance in the Alps	Local authorities (100%)	7 (7)
C40	Local authorities (100%)	48 (13)
City Destination Alliance	Local authorities (94%)	36 (34)
Climate Action Network Europe	Non-profit entities (100%)	38 (37)
Climate Alliance	Local authorities (97%)	26 (24)
Climate Governance Initiative	National networks (100%)	58 (20)
Climate Heritage	Non-profit entities (45%)	47 (19)
Climate-KIC	Other (NA)	NA
Covenant of Mayors - Europe	Local authorities (100)	48 (40)
Energy Cities	Local authorities (86%)	32 (28)
Eurocities	Local authorities (100%)	38 (36)
EUROPARC	National/subnational parks (46%)	39 (34)
European Environment and Sustainable Development Advisory Councils Network	National authorities (90%)	13 (13)
European Environmental Bureau	Non-profit entities (98%)	39 (36)
European Forest Institute	Universities (39%)	38 (32)
European Regions for Competitive and Sustainable Tourism	Regional authorities (56%)	20 (20)
European Sustainable Development Network	National authorities (NA)	33 (33)

FEDARENE - European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and Environment	Regional authorities (71%)	24 (24)
Forest Europe	National authorities (93%)	45 (44)
Fridays For Future	Non-structured movements (100%)	99 (40)
ICLEI Europe - Local Government for Sustainability	Local authorities (93%)	39 (35)
ICPDR - International Committee for the Protection of the Danube River	National authorities (88%)	14 (14)
JPI Climate	National authorities (79%)	19 (19)
Making Cities Resilient 2030	Local authorities (100%)	29 (23)
METREX	Local authorities (76%)	19 (19)
NDC Partnership - Nationally Determined Contributions	National authorities (70%)	129 (19)
Reclaim the Power	Non-structured movements (100%)	1 (1)
Resilient Cities Network	Local authorities (100%)	46 (9)
SDSN Europe - Sustainable Development Solutions Network	Research organizations (100%)	40 (16)
UK Green Building Council	For-profit entities (77%)	1 (1)
Union of the Baltic Cities	Local authorities (96%)	10 (10)
World Green Building Council Europe	National networks (100%)	23 (23)

* Number of European³ countries covered are presented in parentheses.

3.3 Knowledge networks for climate adaptation

3.3.1. General characteristics

Looking at the year in which KN were established, figure 1 shows a striking acceleration in the number of KN being created, going from a maximum of 4 at the end of the 1980s' to 15 at the end of the next decade and 21 at the end of the 2000s'. In 2024, the number of KN tops at 32, which is an eightfold increase in about 35 years.

Figure 1 - Establishment of climate change adaptation-related KN in Europe (1970-2020).

In terms of geographical distribution (figure 2), the countries with the most KNs we identified are Belgium (7), Germany (5), and France (5) and the UK (4), though this may be biased by the English-language aspect of our literature search. Three networks are headquartered outside Europe; 2 in the US and 1 in Singapore.

Figure 2 - Country of Knowledge Networks' headquarters.

Approximately half of the KNs identified operate at the European level, a logical outcome from our inclusion criteria. However, 11 of them have a global outlook, 3 have a regional—as in transnational but circumscribed to a specific area—focus, and 2 have a national focus.

We categorised on two dimensions: 1) whether they address CCA generally (i.e. they tackle several aspects of it) or specifically (i.e. they focus on one field within CCA: ecosystems and biodiversity, climate justice, energy, industry, or weather), and 2) whether they only address CCA or they address it as one issue among others (such as social inclusion, culture, economic development, or migration). Regarding the first dimension, 21 out of 32 KNs address CCA in broad terms, leaving 11 networks with a narrower, more specific, domain of application, including: ecosystems and biodiversity (3 KNs), energy (3), industry (3), climate justice (1), and heritage (1). Regarding the second dimension, considering whether CCA is the KNs' core business or one policy area among others, CCA is the core activity for 17 KNs out of 32 in total. The rest (15) tackles CCA as one issue among other policy areas, *inter alia* circular economy, urban planning, inequalities, tourism, health.

As for the way KN carry out their activities (figure 3, left panel), many of them focus on exchange of good practices and policy-related activities, with respectively 27 and 24 KNs of 32 networks dedicating time and resources to these activities. Conversely, protest and knowledge dissemination are seldom part of their core activities. Research and monitoring of climate change indicators is also less prominent as only 6 KNs consider this as their core activity. KNs' activities are dependent on funding, and in most cases, they have several funding streams. Figure 3, right panel, displays the source of funding they rely on. Note that it does not consider the relative volume of different funding sources as this information could not be retrieved systematically. Overall, the most frequent sources of funding across KN are membership fees (19 out of 32 collect membership fees) and government funding (14 out of 32). EU competitive grants come in third position with 11 KN counting on it, whilst non-EU competitive grants are only mentioned by 4 KNs.

Figure 3 - Knowledge Networks' core activities and funding sources.

3.3.2. Knowledge networks members

The KN we identified vary in size, ranging from 8 members for Reclaim the Power, a UK-based informal protest group, to more than 11,000 for Covenant of Mayors Europe, a transnational network of municipalities. Note that the membership spread is quite large as, excluding the minimum and maximum values, half of them have between 16 (for the International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River) and 99 members (for Resilient Cities Network), the other half between 118 (for Fridays for Future) and 1977 members (for Climate Alliance). Appendix 1 provides more information in this respect. Interestingly, the largest numbers of KN members are located in Italy and Spain, with respectively 5152 and 3111 unique entities², as shown in figure 4. In comparison, Germany and Belgium, where a large proportion of the KN is headquartered, count 826 and 620 unique members.

Figure 4 - Knowledge network members per country.

Figure 5 provides a more detailed description of the location of knowledge network members in Europe. The circles are located in each country's capital and their size represents the number of organisations per country. Note, however, that reasoning in absolute numbers does not account for population size; this should be taken into consideration while interpreting figure 5. Furthermore, a few network members are located well beyond Europe, with a total of 173 countries represented.

Figure 5 - Location of knowledge network members in Europe.

Strikingly, it appears that certain countries are more represented in some networks than others. As shown in figure 6, 42% of the members of Covenant of Mayors are based in Italy, 26% of them are based in Spain. These figures are in stark contrast to Climate Alliance membership, with 55% of their members being based in Austria and 32% in Germany. This is in line with findings presented elsewhere on language, culture, and institutional homophily (see Dawes et al. 2012; Fünfgeld, 2015). Rather than viewing proportions from the network perspective, i.e., the share of members from a given country within a particular network, we can look at it from the country perspective, i.e., considering the share of members of a network within a given country (not graphed), it appears that 93% of all entities based in Italy (that is a total of 5,152 organizations) are members of Covenant of Mayors. This figure rises to 95% for entities based in Spain (out of 3,111 organizations). Considering now Austria and Germany, which respectively count 1,161 and 826 organizations in total, 88% of the Austrian and 67% of the German ones are members of Climate Alliance. This concentration trend is noticeable, albeit less pronounced, across most countries. To name a few examples: 83% of Belgian, 38% of French, 86% of Hungarian, and 59% of Portuguese organizations are member of Covenant of Mayors. This may be connected to a lesser access threshold for Covenant of Mayors as a network. Unlike many other networks, registration for Covenant of Mayors Europe does not require paying a membership fee.

Now that we know where knowledge network members are based, let us dwell on what type of actors are in the KN identified (figure 7). Many of the organizations represented in the data are local authorities³ (85%; 14,047 unique entities out of a total of 16,524), followed by for-profit entities (3.5%), non-profit entities (3.1%), and national authorities (1.6%). Research organizations (comprising both universities and other institutes) represent a sheer 1.1% of membership. Note though that research organizations may be part of networks as associate members (i.e. not full-members) or they may punctually take part in time-limited projects (such as Horizon 2020). Interestingly, networks tend to gather similar organizations within. A total of 9 KN (out of 32) gathers only one type of actor. These tend to be transnational networks of local authorities (e.g. Alliance in the Alps, C40, Climate Alliance). However, some networks chiefly comprising municipalities also gather other types of organizations. This is the case for instance with ICLEI, which gather five types of organizations, among which local and regional authorities, national associations of municipalities and non-profit entities (although 93% of the network's members are municipalities). Only 7 KN gather more than four different types of actors. For instance, Energy Cities, whose members are prevalently cities (86% of its members), also has international organizations, national and regional authorities, and

associations of municipalities as members. Similarly, the UK's branch of the Green Building Council, which counts a majority of for-profit entities (77% of its members), has local, regional and national authorities, universities, and non-profit organizations as members.

Figure 7 - Type of actors and number of actor types within network.

3.3.3. Knowledge networks supporting local authorities

The striking overrepresentation of local authorities within KN begs the question of the reason why they join these networks in the first place. Furthermore, a number of these local authorities choose to join several different networks (figure 8), which further increases the relevance of the question why they join one or several networks, but not some others. While these questions cannot be answered without thorough empirical evidence, we can hypothesise elements of answer by looking at what those networks offer to their members and whether their services differ from one platform to the other. In addition, the choice to join a network is likely related to what a given network requires from them. That is, while different networks provide different services to their members, accessing these networks may require a higher or lower level of commitment. In this section, we delve into the type of support KN provide to their members. We attempt to consider said support in relation to what we call access thresholds, that is, the formal conditions that a potential member must meet to become (or remain) a member of a certain knowledge network. However, the relationship between support provided and access threshold can only be hypothesised at this stage.

The analysis that follows rests on a subset of the 32 KN identified earlier to focus on networks whose members are largely composed of local authorities (at least 50%). Table 4 lists those KN as well as summary information on their focus on adaptation, their members and the criteria required to be part of that KN.

Table 4 – Knowledge networks supporting local authorities on climate change adaptation

Knowledge network	Focus on adaptation	Creation Year	Number of LAs	LAs %	Membership criteria	European ⁴ countries covered
Alliance in the Alps	Addresses CCA generally, along with other themes connected to sustainable development	1997	304	100	i) Being a local authority; ii) located in the Alpine region; ii) fee based on population with range €150 - €2,800	7
C40	Addresses CCA generally	2005	96	100	i) Being a local authority; ii) with exceptional climate leadership; iii) with more than 3 million inhabitants; iv) performance on CCA	13
Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy - Europe	Addresses CCA generally	2008	11610	100	i) Being a local authority	40
Eurocities	Cover a range of themes including climate change	1986	209	100	i) Being a local authority; ii) membership fee (although no further detail provided)	36
Making Cities Resilient 2030 – Europe and Central Asia	Focus on reducing climate risk and building resilience and adaptation	2020	206	100	i) Being a local authority committed to the networks' goals	23
Resilient Cities Network	Focus on resilience at the city level	2020	99	100	i) Being a local authority	9
Climate Alliance	Focus on climate mitigation and adaptation	1990	1908	96.5	i) Being a local authority or indigenous organization; ii) membership fee based on population with range €250 - €15,000	24
Union of the Baltic Cities	Cover a range of themes including	1991	74	96.1	i) Being a local authority; ii) located in the Baltic region; iii) fee based on population	10

	sustainable development (of which climate change is a sub-topic)				with range €600-€7,250	
City Destination Alliance	Addresses CCA focusing on sustainable tourism	2007	115	94.3	i) Two among a) more than 3,000 beds or 1,500 rooms in commercial accommodations; b) capacity to host large meetings; c) hosting at least 3 large international meetings a year; ii) fee based on yearly income with range €2,360 - €5,310	34
ICLEI Europe	Focus on sustainability, resilience and climate neutrality	1992	178	92.7	i) Being a local authority or association of local authorities; ii) fee based on inhabitants and GNP per capita with range €100 - €8,000	35
Energy Cities	Focus on energy transition	1990	157	85.8	i) Being a local authority, association of local government, local energy agency or municipal company; ii) fee based on inhabitants and EU (+GBR, CHE and NOR) membership with range €625 - €5,000	28
Network of European Metropolitan Regions and Areas (Metrex)	Addresses CCA in general, as one urban theme among others	1996	42	76.4	i) Being a metropolitan region or area	19

As mentioned prior, several local authorities choose to join several of the 12 networks presented in table 4. Figure 8 represents the 40 local authorities that are members of more than 4 knowledge networks. Athens, Lisbon and Paris are members in 8 of the 12 networks mentioned; and Barcelona, Rome, Zagreb and Vienna in 7. Local authorities in the north of Europe, including Germany, tend to be present in a lower number of networks compared to their southern counterparts. However, local authorities with multiple memberships in the south tend to be large cities while multiple membership appears to spread to smaller local authorities in the rest of Europe. Taking Germany as an example, Heidelberg has membership in 6 networks and counts less than 160,000 inhabitants; Freiburg im Breisgau is a member of 5 networks and counts about 230,000 inhabitants. In comparison, Rome is about 2.8 million inhabitants, Paris about 2 million, and Barcelona about 1.6 million (Athens and

Lisbon have smaller populations, with respectively about 640,000 and 550,000 inhabitants).

Figure 8 - Number of times a given local authority is present in more than 4 of the 12 networks identified.

Turning to the services local authorities may receive from these networks, the areas of support they can find within KN can be classified in four broad categories as follows: knowledge circulation and CCA expertise, financial support, mediation and peer learning, and symbolic capital. The subsections that follow address these items in turn. Analysis rests on the contents found on the networks' official websites and should thus be considered with caution as the information may not be exhaustive. Before proceeding with the analysis of KN's areas of support, it is necessary to dwell on KN's access thresholds as access criteria and extent of services provided may well be connected. Accessing networks is most often based on prospective members applying for membership, passing a local bill bearing witness to their commitments to the goals of the network, and some level of vetting process whereby the network's governing body accepts an application. In addition to this widely applied process, there are additional criteria that potential members may have to meet to become part of the network. These criteria may be distributed in three tiers: i) networks with low access thresholds, for which no (or low) membership fees are required and no other condition should be met (e.g. Covenant of Mayors or MCR2030); ii) networks with a medium access threshold, with higher membership fees and potentially stringent additional conditions (e.g. being part of a specific region as for Alliance in the Alps or Union of the Baltic Cities); and iii) selective networks which apply a high access threshold, which is the case only for C40 which requires their members to display exceptional leadership in CCA, to have more than 3 million inhabitants or be CCA innovators, and to achieve measurable results on the matter.

Knowledge circulation and CCA expertise

Knowledge networks provide CCA knowledge and expertise to improve the substance and effectiveness of their members' actions on climate change adaptation and related areas. This chiefly takes three shapes: (1) CCA expertise (the "what" to do), (2) policy knowledge (the "how" to do it; including planning and implementation), and/or (3) progress monitoring (the "what has been done"). Table 5 summarises how knowledge networks address these three aspects.

Starting with CCA expertise, some networks act as knowledge repository where members may find information about CCA policies as implemented in other places, comparative reports, or case studies that may inform their policies and adaptation goals. The role of the network in this instance is mostly that of a mediator which stores knowledge and facilitates its circulation within the network. This is notably the case for C40 with its knowledge hub⁵, Resilient Cities Network with its resource centre⁶, or ICLEI with its publications and tools page⁷. However, the network itself may also be the source of CCA expertise. It is the case with Resilient Cities Network which, together with the member city's staff, develop an assessment of risks and vulnerabilities to inform and plan the city's action strategy. RCN's activity in this respect is accompanied with a series of tools⁸ available to the member city.

Differently, knowledge networks provide significant governance knowledge as a way to improve cities' capacity to plan, design, and implement CCA strategies and policies. The European branch of Covenant of Mayors supports its members in their efforts to plan, implement and monitor adaptation actions through its Policy Support Facility⁹, which provides methodological guidance, technical assistance and activities to build municipalities' capacity to tackle adaptation. Similarly, C40's Climate Action Planning Framework¹⁰ aims to support cities in developing climate action plans to meet the objectives of the Paris Agreement to stay within the 1.5°C temperature increase. C40 also offers a Climate Budgeting Programme to help cities plan and incorporate climate budgeting within their overall city governance. Climate Alliance and ICLEI also propose to provide strategic recommendations to their members, although it comes with an additional fee in the case of ICLEI.

Finally, some networks serve as a platform to monitor progress on climate change adaptation goals. Progress monitoring may either be self-reported or enforced. Cases of self-reporting are most common (3 out of 4). Covenant of Mayors Europe allows members to report and update their commitments and the extent to which they meet their objectives. MCR2030 features member cities dashboards where detailed information is provided by the cities themselves (although only members can see other cities' dashboards). City Destination Alliance also provides a platform featuring data and insights on the latest performance of other members. As for enforced monitoring, this is only the case of C40 which reviews each member city's achievements, every year, against minimum standards established by the network. Cities that do not meet the requirements for 12 consecutive months are categorised as inactive. Thereupon, should cities persistently fail to comply with C40's minimum standards, their membership may be revoked altogether.

Some networks do not expressly provide CCA knowledge and expertise, although they do contribute to these goals via facilitating interactions among members and peer learning. This is the case of the networks mentioned in the next section.

Table 5 – Knowledge circulation and CCA expertise

Knowledge network	CCA expertise	Policy knowledge	Monitor progress
Alliance in the Alps			
C40	✓	✓	✓
Covenant of Mayors Europe	✓	✓	✓
Eurocities			
Making Cities Resilient 2030	✓		✓
Resilient Cities Network	✓		
Climate Alliance	✓	✓	
Union of the Baltic Cities			
City Destination Alliance			✓
ICLEI Europe	✓	✓	
Energy Cities	✓	✓	
Metrex			

Financial resources and support

Financial opportunities are essential for local authorities which are diversely endowed with personnel, resources, and ability to borrow on capital markets (Carter and Boukerche, 2020; Gyévai and Jávora, 2023). KN financial support can be categorised in three main strands: support in applying for funding, facilitating consortium building and project leading, and directly funding municipalities' projects. Table 6 below summarises the type of financial support provided by the 12 networks under scrutiny. Half of the KN provide general assistance in obtaining funds from financing bodies, often from the EU's various schemes. Support may be informative or technical, and whether it is the one or the other is likely connected to the networks' access threshold. Informative support revolves around informing members of the various types of funding opportunities available. For example, Covenant of Mayors Europe, which is hosted and maintained by the European Commission, offers an extensive funding opportunities search engine¹¹, allowing municipalities (members of the network or not) to navigate the various EU programmes connected to climate change adaptation, mitigation, and energy. Similarly, Eurocities (and to some extent Climate Alliance) offers to inform its members about funding schemes available to them via funding briefs and forecasts as to upcoming EU funding opportunities. Beyond information provision, some other networks propose technical assistance as a way to increase local authorities' chances to obtain funding. C40's Cities Finance Facility¹², for instance, provides tailored technical assistance to develop cities' sustainability priorities into bankable investment proposals. Likewise, ICLEI Europe provides advice to its members to help them obtain the funding necessary for them to tackle their goals and priorities.

Another key activity consists in facilitating consortium building and project leading. Five out of our twelve networks serve as a platform for their members to interact and, possibly, find partners to apply for EU funding. This is the case of Alliance in the Alps, Eurocities, Climate Alliance, ICLEI Europe, and Energy Cities. Energy Cities, whose activities are distributed among five thematic hubs, provides for each of them a marketplace where potential candidates can form consortia and apply for major

international funding schemes. In addition to facilitating consortium building among their members, knowledge networks may also lead or take part in projects alongside them. Considering for instance EU-funded research and innovation projects¹³, ICLEI Europe has participated in 172 projects (8% of which as project coordinator), Eurocities in 46 (7% as coordinator), and Energy Cities in 31 (16% of which as coordinator).

Direct funding is less common and it's only available in one of the networks studied. Through its Resilient Community Impact Funds¹⁴, Resilient Cities Network raises funds from investors to support specific, small to medium scale, projects to take place in its member cities. The fund focuses on projects that enhance community resilience, accelerate transition to clean energy, promote waste reduction, and foster equitable development. It targeted a goal of raising \$10 million by 2024, with initial contributions from major partners like Bank of America and the Z Zurich Foundation. Importantly, not all networks appear to address the financial aspects of CCA, as the core activities of City Destination Alliance, Union of the Baltic Cities, and Making Cities Resilient 2030 lie elsewhere.

Table 6 – Financial resources and support

Knowledge network	General assistance	Consortium building	Direct funding
Alliance in the Alps		✓	
C40	✓		
Covenant of Mayors Europe	✓		
Eurocities	✓	✓	
Making Cities Resilient 2030			
Resilient Cities Network			✓
Climate Alliance	✓	✓	
Union of the Baltic Cities			
City Destination Alliance			
ICLEI Europe	✓	✓	
Energy Cities		✓	
Metrex	✓		

Collaboration and peer learning

Collaboration and peer learning is an essential activity of all networks gathering municipalities. It is also the one element that is common to all of them. More precisely, networks aim to foster, organize, and facilitate connections among members with similar interests by providing occasions of encounter, be they virtual or physical. Networks may convene annual conferences, pursue thematic groups, or maintain online platforms and other intranet spaces where members can meet, interact, exchange information and expertise, or build partnerships to apply for external funding. Table 7 summarizes networks' role fulfilled through general conferences, and thematic workshops or working groups.

Alliance in the Alps' main goal is to facilitate the exchange of experiences and expertise within a community of members distributed across 7 countries and which

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share concerns about the preservation of the Alpine region. The network organizes conferences, workshops and webinars for its members on a regular basis. Union of the Baltic Cities operate in a similar fashion for the 9 countries bordering the Baltic Sea. Differently, Energy Cities provides five online thematic hubs as community spaces where member cities can exchange on specific topics. Table 7 summarises the ways in which networks facilitate peer learning through interaction.

Table 7 – Collaboration and Peer Learning

Knowledge network	Conferences	Thematic groups
Alliance in the Alps	✓	✓
C40	✓	
Covenant of Mayors Europe	✓	
Eurocities	✓	✓
Making Cities Resilient 2030	✓	✓
Resilient Cities Network	✓	✓
Climate Alliance	✓	✓
Union of the Baltic Cities	✓	✓
City Destination Alliance	✓	✓
ICLEI Europe	✓	✓
Energy Cities	✓	✓
Metrex	✓	✓

Symbolic capital

Beyond practical returns on membership, some networks also provide symbolic capital which contributes to cities accumulated reputational power. Symbolic markers help convey a certain image which communicates commitment to climate change adaptation beyond actual achievement or substantial change (Kern and Bulkeley, 2009). These are political resources which increase the standing of a municipality, both on the international stage towards its peers and at the domestic level for voters interested in the actions taken by their most proximate policymakers. Being part of an international network of municipalities brings about symbolic resources by the mere fact of being a member, but said resources may also be proactively provided by the networks themselves. For instance, Kern and Bulkeley (2009) have noted how the majority of member cities part of Climate Alliance are relatively passive, thus making membership a rather symbolic one. From the network's end, Climate Alliance may be reinforcing symbolic returns through increased visibility of membership, even if not accompanied with action. For instance, one of the membership benefits advertised¹⁵ in the network's official website is the ability to display the logo "We are Climate Alliance" to "strengthen [the city's] profile regionally, nationally and internationally!" (emphasis in the original). City Destination Alliance advertises¹⁶ a similar type of benefit and argues that membership enhances visibility and recognition through sheer membership.

From a different perspective, some networks also provide symbolic returns by emphasising CCA accomplishments through prizes awarded to their members. Via its Climate Star competition, Climate Alliance aims to recognise Europe's best municipal action by awarding a star to excellent projects carried out by its members.

Similarly, ICLEI Europe grants the ICLEI Sustainability Award for shared governance, integrated finance and cohesive transition, while Eurocities grant three prizes, for innovative ecosystems, sustainable food systems, and creative election campaigns.

Table 8 – Symbolic capital

Knowledge network	Advertised visibility benefit	Award benefit
Alliance in the Alps		
C40		
Covenant of Mayors Europe		
Eurocities		✓
Making Cities Resilient 2030		
Resilient Cities Network		
Climate Alliance	✓	✓
Union of the Baltic Cities		
City Destination Alliance	✓	
ICLEI Europe		✓
Energy Cities		
Metrex		

3.4 Discussion

Our analysis highlighted the current landscape of KN that support CCA in Europe. The 32 KN identified provide a range of resources and opportunities of collaborating and learning.

The two core activities KNs primarily engage in is exchange of good practices as well as policy support and advocacy. The emphasis on these activities likely reflects the specific needs and operational realities of their main members, particularly those largely composed of LA. The exchange of good practices may provide LA with a diverse array of insights and frameworks that can be adapted to their local contexts. Additionally, the varying levels of resources and expertise across LA may make the exchange of good practices and policy guidance more feasible than other more resource-intensive activities such as direct activities and implementation (Fünfgeld, 2015). Advocacy, in turn, may serve to amplify member voices and align local efforts with broader national and international climate goals. Surprisingly, knowledge dissemination, arguably central to KNs' mission, appears less common among all KNs. This gap raises questions about how effectively KN are fulfilling their multiple roles (Creech et al., 2004).

Furthermore, there is very little information on the effect of the support offered by KN on their members' adaptation efforts and outcomes (Hauge et al., 2018; Woodruff, 2020). While good practices and policy guidance may be crucial, the lack of systematic monitoring might limit these networks' capacity to gauge and enhance their members' adaptation success. In addition, research focusing on how KN membership influences internal decision-making

within member organisations (such as LA) can also help understand how to maximise opportunities and the support provided by KN (Busch et al., 2018; Heikkinen et al., 2020).

The distribution of KN members is highly uneven, with a marked concentration in certain countries, particularly Italy and Spain. Some KN also show strong national clustering; for example, Covenant of Mayors is primarily composed of members from Italy and Spain, while Climate Alliance has a high representation from Austria and Germany. The factors driving these patterns require further study but may include greater engagement by LA in these countries, historical affiliations with certain networks, language, or localized efforts that have been especially successful in attracting membership (Kern and Bulkeley, 2009). Additionally, factors such as membership affordability, political support, and targeted promotion within specific regions may also contribute to these concentrations (*ibid*; Busch et al., 2018).

Membership conditions—criteria that prospective members must meet to join a network—also vary considerably among KN. Networks with low thresholds, such as the Covenant of Mayors, allow for easy entry and may attract a larger, more diverse membership base. In contrast, selective networks like C40 have higher thresholds, requiring members to demonstrate significant climate leadership and capacity. While high-threshold networks may indeed have more committed and potentially higher-performing members, lower-threshold networks might attract some members primarily interested in symbolic affiliation—joining to signal support for climate adaptation without necessarily committing to substantial action (Fünfgeld, 2015; Kern and Bulkeley, 2009). Further research is needed to understand how membership thresholds correlate with network effectiveness and LA performance in CCA (cf. Bauer and Steurer, 2014).

3.5 Conclusion

Our study identified 32 KN characterized by interactive, multi-directional knowledge exchange. The landscape of these KN is multifaceted, with networks varying widely in core aims and objectives, geographic distribution, size, and member composition. While some focus exclusively on CCA, others address CCA alongside issues like social inclusion, culture, economic development, or migration. Most KN headquarters are based in Belgium, Germany, and France, though membership is highly concentrated in certain countries, notably Italy and Spain. KN size varies dramatically, from as few as 8 members to over 11,000. Across all networks, 85% of members are LA, followed by for-profit and non-profit entities, and national authorities. Only 12 of the 32 KNs have memberships that are at least 50% LA.

Future research on KN for climate adaptation should seek to explore some of the discussion points raised by this study namely examine how effective are the different KN in performing their multiple roles; which roles are most effective in supporting

members (particularly LA) in their adaptation efforts; and what are the impacts of these KN in enabling/supporting adaptation outcomes.

3.6 Appendix 1: List of Knowledge Networks and Knowledge Hubs

Platforms name	Platforms' type	Main type of members (%)	Total number of countries covered (European ³ countries in parentheses)
Alliance in the Alps	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (100%)	7 (7)
C40	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (100%)	48 (13)
City Destination Alliance	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (94%)	36 (34)
Climate Action Network Europe	Knowledge Network	Non-profit entities (100%)	38 (37)
Climate Alliance	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (97%)	26 (24)
Climate Governance Initiative	Knowledge Network	National networks (100)	58 (20)
Climate Heritage	Knowledge Network	Non-profit entities (45%)	47 (19)
Climate-KIC	Knowledge Network	Other (NA)	NA
Covenant of Mayors - Europe	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (100)	48 (40)
Energy Cities	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (86%)	32 (28)
Eurocities	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (100%)	38 (36)
EUROPARC	Knowledge Network	National/subnational parks (46%)	39 (34)
European Environment and Sustainable Development Advisory Councils Network	Knowledge Network	National authorities (90%)	13 (13)
European Environmental Bureau	Knowledge Network	Non-profit entities (98%)	39 (36)
European Forest Institute	Knowledge Network	Universities (39%)	38 (32)
European Regions for Competitive and Sustainable Tourism	Knowledge Network	Regional authorities (56%)	20 (20)
European Sustainable Development Network	Knowledge Network	National authorities (NA)	33 (33)
FEDARENE - European Federation of Agencies	Knowledge Network	Regional authorities (71%)	24 (24)

and Regions for Energy and Environment			
Forest Europe	Knowledge Network	National authorities (93%)	45 (44)
Fridays For Future	Knowledge Network	Non-structured movements (100%)	99 (40)
ICLEI Europe - Local Government for Sustainability	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (93%)	39 (35)
ICPDR - International Committee for the Protection of the Danube River	Knowledge Network	National authorities (88%)	14 (14)
JPI Climate	Knowledge Network	National authorities (79%)	19 (19)
Making Cities Resilient 2030	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (100%)	29 (23)
METREX	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (76%)	19 (19)
NDC Partnership - Nationally Determined Contributions	Knowledge Network	National authorities (70%)	129 (19)
Reclaim the Power	Knowledge Network	Non-structured movements (100%)	1 (1)
Resilient Cities Network	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (100%)	46 (9)
SDSN Europe - Sustainable Development Solutions Network	Knowledge Network	Research organizations (100%)	40 (16)
UK Green Building Council	Knowledge Network	For-profit entities (77%)	1 (1)
Union of the Baltic Cities	Knowledge Network	Local authorities (96%)	10 (10)
World Green Building Council Europe	Knowledge Network	National networks (100%)	23 (23)
Alliance for Global Water Adaptation	Knowledge Hub	International NGO (NA)	1 (0)
Climate Change Committee	Knowledge Hub	Public authority (NA)	1 (1)
Climate Knowledge Portal	Knowledge Hub	Intergovernmental platform (NA)	NA
Climate-ADAPT	Knowledge Hub	Intergovernmental platform (NA)	27 (27)
Copernicus	Knowledge Hub	Intergovernmental platform (NA)	35 (35)
European Commission's Joint Research Centre	Knowledge Hub	Intergovernmental platform (NA)	27 (27)
European Environment Agency	Knowledge Hub	Intergovernmental platform (NA)	38 (38)

Green Peace UK	Knowledge Hub	National NGO (NA)	1 (1)
Julie's bicycle	Knowledge Hub	National NGO (NA)	1 (1)
Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies	Knowledge Hub	National research institution (NA)	1 (1)
Nature Conservancy	Knowledge Hub	Intergovernmental platform (NA)	NA
Sustainable and Just Cities	Knowledge Hub	Public authority (NA)	39 (39)
Sustainable Cities Platform	Knowledge Hub	Other (NA)	NA
weADAPT	Knowledge Hub	Other (NA)	1 (1)

3.7 Work Carried Out

NORCE colleagues conducted the work in task 1.1. and deliverable 1.1. with project partners providing feedback and comments at key points in the process. This deliverable was originally expected in month 12 but due to delays in hiring a post-doc to work on this task in the initial months of the project an extension was requested for submission in month 25.

3.8 Status of Knowledge

See above.

3.9 Main Results Achieved

The Deliverable provides a comprehensive analysis of the landscape of KN operating in the field of CCA in Europe, thus directly supporting the objectives outlined in WP1 and T1.1.

Mapping the Landscape of KN: The document identifies 32 Knowledge Networks and 14 Knowledge Hubs, categorizing them based on their activities (e.g., advocacy, peer learning) and modes of operation (e.g., unidirectional knowledge dissemination or multidirectional collaboration). This aligns with the task's aim to take stock of the current KN landscape.

Actor Analysis: It details the types of members in KNs, such as local authorities, non-profit organizations, for-profits, and research institutions. This includes an in-depth examination of member composition and representation across countries, addressing the task's focus on the actors involved.

Roles in Supporting Adaptation: The document explores how KNs support climate adaptation through activities like policy advocacy, financial capacity building, and knowledge circulation. This directly addresses the task's need to understand the role of KNs in supporting adaptation measures.

Governance Structures: KN governance models are described, including membership thresholds, and funding mechanisms. This insight supports the task's goal of analyzing how KNs are governed.

Use of Climate Information and Identified Needs: The document discusses the ways KNs facilitate knowledge sharing, use climate information, and support local authorities in addressing specific adaptation challenges. It also identifies gaps, such as limited monitoring of adaptation outcomes, contributing to understanding KNs' current needs.

The deliverable also provides insights to inform subsequent tasks, such as identifying relevant networks for engagement in T1.3 and T1.4.

3.10 Progress Beyond State of the Art

This paper advances current knowledge on current KN supporting climate adaptation in Europe. Whilst there are studies examining specific KN supporting climate-related activities including those supporting local authorities, there is a gap in knowledge regarding an up to date understanding and analysis of recent KN that have emerged in Europe in recent years following a recent emphasis on the urgent need to adapt to the risks of climate change in Europe (e.g. following adoption of the EU adaptation strategy in 2021). This also contributes to an understanding of the overall landscape of this type of KN currently operating in Europe as well as the type of support they provide to their members towards enabling adaptation efforts.

4 Impact

The deliverable's impact is both scientific and societal. First, D1.1 contributes to extant literature on knowledge networks and climate change adaptation. It is the first attempt to comprehensively map the landscape of KNs concerned with CCA in Europe. By identifying 46 platforms, analyzing 32 KNs and focusing on 12 Transnational Municipal Networks, the deliverable provides a robust foundation for understanding the breadth and diversity of climate change adaptation networks, including activist groups, municipal alliances, and research hubs. The in-depth analysis of KN members—predominantly local authorities but also including non-profits, for-profits, and research entities—clarifies the types of stakeholders engaged in adaptation efforts.

The deliverable also has societal impacts. It sets the stage for the uptake, integration and usability of climate information produced in the project as a whole. By providing essential information on networks, their members, their functioning, and their activities, D1.1 is instrumental to the work being conducted in T1.3 and T1.4 as it offers a list of potentially relevant networks for engagement, ensuring strategic targeting of KNs that align with the project's objectives, and unlocking broader impacts of WP1. Furthermore, by mapping the landscape of KNs in Europe, D1.1 lays the groundwork for improved circulation of knowledge created by the project as a whole.

5 Links Built

The deliverable is mostly linked with the other deliverables to be produced within WP1. First, by reviewing academic and grey literature, D1.1 informs the Agent-Based Model of knowledge circulation built in T1.2. More specifically, the analytical framework findings presented in the deliverable contribute to the elaboration of assumptions on network members' behaviour. Second, by mapping the landscape of networks concerned with CCA in Europe, D1.1 allows the identification of other relevant networks to be engaged with (T1.3) and the exploration of opportunities to scale up the findings put forth in the I4C Demonstrator cities within a larger ensemble of knowledge networks (T1.4). The link built between the deliverable (T1.1) and T1.4 connects the deliverable with the goals of WP6 ("Co-production of I4C Demonstrators")

and, more generally with the results produced in WP2 through WP5. In so doing, the deliverable is in line with the EU's Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change on building “resilience against the impacts of climate change”¹

6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

The activities connected to Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation in relation to D1.1 can thus far be categorised in two groups. The first one regards communication and dissemination of results in academic conferences. To date, the deliverable was presented once at the European Meteorological Society Conference 2024 in Barcelona, Spain. Its abstract was submitted for participation at the European Political Science Association Conference 2025, to take place in Madrid, Spain, in June 2025. The same abstract will also be submitted for participation at the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference 2025, Rimini, Italy, June 2025. The second group of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities concerns the storage of the data produced in T1.1 on Sikt, the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research. In so doing, the data will become available to the scientific community at large, in accordance with the FAIR principles—Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities in relation to this deliverable include:

Communication and dissemination in academic conferences:

- European Meteorological Society Conference 2024 (deliverable presented)
- European Political Science Association Conference 2025 (abstract submitted)
- European Climate Change Adaptation Conference 2025 (abstract and propose session on KN to be submitted)

Dissemination of data for exploitation by scientific community:

- Database on KNs in Europe and their characteristics (in progress)
- Database on KNs' members in Europe (in progress)

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/adaptation-climate-change_en

6.1 Peer Reviewed Articles

The deliverable will be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal shortly. Its pre-print version will also be published on Zenodo and OpenAIRE. The reference below is temporary and will be updated once the article will be accepted for publication

1. Bruno Soares M., Van Wolleghem P.G., Lamb G., Puga-Gonzalez I. (to be submitted) "The Landscape of Knowledge Networks Supporting Climate Change Adaptation in Europe" *Journal to be determined*.

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